

Cretan Archers and the Cretan Countermarch

We have already seen the ubiquity of the Cretan archer in ancient armies from at least the late fifth century BCE onwards until the late Roman Republic. The question should be asked therefore, what set these archers apart from any other type of archers and made them so attractive to employ as mercenaries above other groups. Unfortunately, our sources are generally silent on this matter but there is one tantalising possibility suggested in our sources which seems to have been overlooked.

It is, of course, possible that Cretan archers were better at archery than their counterparts – and certainly the ancient association with Crete and the bow would suggest that they prided themselves on the proficiency in a weapon shunned by the rest of Greece. But in comparison with other types of bowmen, Cretan superiority does not seem so assured – we know from Xenophon (*Anabasis* 3.3.6-18) that Persian bows outdistanced Cretan ones. This detail would seem to discount the idea that the Cretan bow itself was superior to other types and perhaps that the draw of Cretan bowmen was superior. Perhaps Cretan bowmen were more accurate, even if they could not shoot as far as their Persian pursuers in the *Anabasis*. More than that, Cretan archer contingents were not necessarily large and yet still present in armies of much larger masses of troops. Even when present in relatively small numbers, our sources consider it noteworthy (or necessary) that the Cretan contingent be named and numbered. Thus, Thucydides tells us of the 80 Cretans who made up part of the 480 archers for the Sicilian expedition (6.43). We should ask why such a relatively small number of Cretan archers should be considered noteworthy or effective (and presumably such small contingents proved they were). Even when numbers of Cretan archers expand into the thousands (such as the 2,000 employed by Ptolemy IV at the battle of Raphia in 217 BCE (Polybius 5.65.7)), they are still only a small part of the make-up of the whole army (at Raphia, Ptolemy had 70,000 infantry). Perseus' 3,000 Cretan archers in 171 BCE were part of a force of 39,000 infantry (Livy 42.51.7-11). Cretan archers remained a common feature of Greek and Roman armies for the next four centuries after the battle of Cunaxa in 401 BCE.

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discount that the Cretan bow itself was superior and perhaps that the draw of Cretan bowmen was superior. Perhaps they were more accurate, even if they could not shoot as far as their Persian pursuers in the *Anabasis*. More than that, Cretan archer contingents were not necessarily large and yet still present in armies of much larger masses of troops. Even when present in relatively small numbers (such as 80 out of 480 archers on the Sicilian expedition (Thucydides 6.43)), our sources consider it noteworthy that the Cretan contingent be named and numbered. We should ask why a relatively small number of Cretan archers would be considered noteworthy or effective (and presumably such small contingents proved they were). Even when numbers of Cretan archers expand into the thousands (such as the 2,000 employed by Ptolemy IV at the battle of Raphia in 217 BCE (Polybius 5.65.7)), they are still only a small part of the make-up of the whole army (at Raphia, Ptolemy had 70,000 infantry). Perseus' 3,000 Cretan archers in 171 BCE were part of a force of 39,000 infantry (Livy 42.51.7-11). It cannot simply have been that they were the cheapest option or else why hire them in such (relatively) small numbers. Cretan archers remained a common feature of Greek and Roman armies for the next four centuries after the Sicilian expedition in 415 BCE.

One possibility for why contingents of Cretan archers were set apart suggests itself from the evidence of the Greek *Tactica* and the existence of a specific manoeuvre known as the Cretan Countermarch.

We have three *Tactica* treatises surviving from antiquity (by Asclepiodotus, Aelian and Arrian). These treatises describe the marshalling and tactics of the Macedonian phalanx of Alexander the Great and later Hellenistic phalanxes. These treatises had a rich history reaching back, at least to Pyrrhus of Epirus (Aelian *Tactica* 1) but continued to be written well into the Roman period despite the fact that these treatises described an obsolete formation. In the earliest surviving treatise, Asclepiodotus' *Tactica Theoria*, which is usually dated to the late 50s BCE, the author describes three countermarches used by the Macedonian/Hellenistic phalanx (*Tactica* 10.13-15). The first two (10.13-14), the Macedonian and the Laconian, allowed the phalanx to occupy ground to the rear or the front of their current position. The association of a countermarch named after the Laconians or the Macedonians causes no concern, both names being entirely appropriate for a phalanx of spearmen. The third countermarch, however, does cause some disquiet:

The so-called Cretan and Persian countermarch is an intermediate between the two; for it does not occupy the position behind the phalanx, as the Macedonian, nor the one before the phalanx, as the Laconian, but occupies the same ground, while the

file-leader takes the place of the file-closer, and in like manner the rear-rank-men those of the front-rank-men . . . marching past each other, and this in two ways, either by file or by rank, until the file-closer has in turn taken the place of the file-leader. That is, consider the line of file-leaders $\alpha \beta \gamma \delta \epsilon$, of rear-rank-men $\zeta \eta \theta \iota \kappa$, then $\lambda \mu \nu \xi \omicron$, and after it as the rank of file-closers $\pi \rho \sigma \tau \upsilon$; then $\alpha \beta \gamma \delta \epsilon$ takes the position of $\pi \rho \sigma \tau \upsilon$, $\zeta \eta \theta \iota \kappa$ of $\lambda \mu \nu \xi \omicron$, $\lambda \mu \nu \xi \omicron$ that of $\zeta \eta \theta \iota \kappa$, and $\pi \rho \sigma \tau \upsilon$ that of $\alpha \beta \gamma \delta \epsilon$. By this countermarch the phalanx will not change its ground, and this we shall find advantageous, whenever the terrain before and behind is less favourable.

Asclepiodotus included an illustration to show what he meant:

This passage is repeated broadly in the other two *Tactica* both of which date to the second century CE (Aelian (*Tactica* 27.1-28.3) and Arrian (*Tactica* 23)). According to Aelian (and Arrian), this manoeuvre was also known as the *chorios* countermarch. The name of ‘Cretan’ is the most dominant for the manoeuvre, however. As a phalanx tactic, it was useful because it allowed the troops to occupy the same space and it allowed them to face to the rear and meet a threat from that quarter.

We should question why a manoeuvre for a Macedonian or Hellenistic phalanx was named after the Cretans and Persians when neither of those cultures’ military forces were associated with anything resembling phalanx tactics. Both the Cretans and the Persians were associated overwhelmingly with the bow. The idea of the spear representing Greek warfare (or indeed western warfare) as opposed to the arrow representing Persia (or the east) goes back as far as Aeschylus’ *Persae* (lines 85-6, 147-9) and continued to be recognised. Diogenes Laertius (5.5) discussed Aristotle’s use of the same imagery. Yet here we find two different types of bowmen associated

with the same manoeuvre for a formation of spearmen. Before we can ponder this question fully it is necessary to leap forward in time some 1,600 years or more to the reforms of European warfare in the late 16th century.

The Cretan countermarch specifically inspired Willem Lodewijk (William Louis) of Nassau to invent the European countermarch (initially described as a ‘conversion’) for musket volley fire in the late 16th century.¹ William Louis, having read Aelian’s *Tactica*, wrote to his cousin Maurits on December 8, 1594 (The Hague Koninklijke Huisarchieff, MS. A22-IXE-79) that he had found²:

‘a method suitable not only for training the musketeers and calivermen to fire, but maintain that this method can very easily be used in battle order ... and that everyone can fire carefully and well, in the following manner: namely that as soon as the first rank has fired simultaneously it steps back *per evolutionem et versum* [i.e. makes and about-turn and returns to the rear of the block]; the second [rank] steps forward or stands still and shoots simultaneously, then marches back; the third and the following do the same. Thus before the last rank has fired, the first rank has reloaded.’

William Louis attached a diagram to explain his formation. He had the formation 9 files across and five ranks deep and showed the position rank ‘a’ would take up after firing³:

We should note the remarkable similarity between William Louis’ illustration and that of Asclepiodotus (who William Louis did not read, indeed the *editio princeps* of Asclepiodotus by Issac Casaubon did not appear until 1609). The illustration in Asclepiodotus shows a formation five files across and four ranks deep.

¹ See Geoffrey Parker *The Military Revolution*, Second Edition, (Cambridge, 1996), p. 19 and n; and Olaf van Nimwegen *The Dutch Army and the Military Revolutions 1588-1688*, translated by Andrew May (Woodbridge, Suffolk, 2010), p. 289.

² Translation from Olaf van Nimwegen ‘The Tactical Military Revolution and Dutch Army Operations during the Era of the Twelve Years Truce (1592-1618) in Randall Lesaffer (ed.) *The Twelve Years Truce (1609)* (Leiden, 2014), pp. 121-151, at p. 134.

³ Source: Wikimedia Commons, author Yprpygp, accessed December 2, 2016.

William Louis' formation was different to the formation described in Aelian who had files (*lochos*) of 16 men (*Tactica* 8.3) and suggests countermarching by *syntagma* (*Tactica* 27.6); a *syntagma* consisted of sixteen files, 256 men (conveniently forming a square of sixteen ranks by sixteen files). William Louis' remarkable insight, inspiration and innovation in reading this tactic involved every soldier in the formation's ranks to discharge their musket at the front of the formation when ordered to, and then countermarch by rank to the rear where they could reload whilst moving again toward the front of the formation. Initially ten ranks of musketeers were required in practice to maintain a continuous rate of fire (not the five William Louis estimated would be needed). William Louis owned four editions of the *Tactica* of Aelian as well as four of the *Tactica* of Leo VI from the 9th century.⁴ As Olaf van Nimwegen contends⁵: 'the development of a method that made orderly volley fire possible is widely considered to be one of the most important military innovations of the early modern era.'

It is interesting to note that William Louis considered that the tactic was a Roman army drill (Aelian was writing in c. 113 CE) and that, in his reading, it was used by rotating ranks of javelinmen or slingers who achieved a constant rate of fire. There is nothing in the *Tactica* of this – the formation was used by the phalanx to face the rear of its current position. What is more, no Roman or Greek history mentions this tactic as applied to missile troops although the idea of a hail of enemy fire is often mentioned. William Louis makes a further alteration to the manoeuvre described in his letter by having the files countermarch to the left (away from the musket of his comrades) whereas in Aelian the march is made 'spearward' (28.3). William Louis' reading of this tactic, incorrect though it was, did lead to a revolutionary new tactic in European warfare which enabled armies throughout the continent to adopt musketry volley-fire using this countermarch. Troops were trained to fire, countermarch, load and manoeuvre all at the same time.

Reverse Engineering the Dutch Master

If we reverse engineer William Louis' tactical innovation, take into consideration his (mis)understanding that the manoeuvre had originally been intended for missile troops, and ponder the name 'Cretan' for it, it is possible that this countermarch was originally a Cretan tactic for maintaining a continuous rate of archery fire. Using this tactic the troops would fire, retire and reload just as their musket wielding successors would. This is perhaps a reason why Cretan archers

⁴ Olaf van Nimwegen 'The Tactical Military Revolution', p. 128.

⁵ Olaf van Nimwegen *The Dutch Army and the Military Revolutions, 1588-1688*, translated by Andrew May (Woodbridge, Suffolk, 2010), p. 289. (Originally '*Deser landen krijchsvolck' Het Staatse leger en de militaire revoluties 1588-1688* (2006)).

were considered so effective for so long, even in relatively small numbers within the armies of antiquity; they could maintain a constant rate of (presumably accurate) fire even with relatively small numbers. Just as William Louis⁶ could recognise the applicability of the countermarch as described in the *Tactica* of Aelian and adapt it for his purposes with musketeers in the 16th century, it is possible that phalanx commanders saw the applicability of a Cretan or Persian manoeuvre and adapted it for their purposes in the phalanx in the 4th century BCE. In both cases the spark of inspiration and the genius of adaptation need to be recognised.

Returning to our question in regard to the naming of a phalanx countermarch after a culture associated with archery, we can suggest why this countermarch was named after the Cretans, or indeed, the Persians. The relevance of the other two countermarches, the Macedonian and Laconian, need no explanation. For the Cretan or Persian countermarch, the association with Cretans is perplexing. It is possible that Persian infantry may have used the same manoeuvre and this was subsequently copied by the Cretans and became primarily associated with them. If manoeuvres for the Macedonian phalanx were developed in the 4th century and after, this was at a time when Cretan archers were ubiquitous during the late fifth and throughout the fourth century BCE. Especially after the defeat of the Persian empire, it would be natural, since Cretan units continued to be used, that the association of the manoeuvre with its possible Persian parent was less emphasised. The *chorios* name may have been later still or came about from a separate association. This is also precisely the period during which the Macedonian countermarch would have become known although, probably, later than the countermarch known as the Laconian. It is also possible, however, that the Laconian countermarch was still in use in Sparta at least in the first four decades of the fourth century and perhaps adopted by later Macedonian armies. The Laconian countermarch may date from earlier hoplite tactics but at no time in its prior history are Cretan troops associated with any particular dominance which might give rise to a specifically ‘Cretan’ countermarch. The only time they can be considered to have dominated a ‘tactic’ was in their providing units of archers. The idea and alternative name of a *chorios* or ‘dancing’ countermarch (not present in Asclepiodotus) is glossed by referring to the importance of dance for hoplite training.⁶ This may reflect a desire to find a more logical ‘heavy infantry’ etymology for a tactic whose other two names derived from archery based troops. There is also the presence of dancing in training of heavy infantry (as well as in the training of Cretans) as can be seen in Strabo (10.4.16) and Polybius (4.20.6-12).

⁶ James DeVoto’s note to Arrian *Tactica* 23.1 and Christopher Matthew’s note to Aelian *Tactica* 26.1 (*The Tactics of Aelian* (Barnsley, 2012)).

It is quite possible that the original Cretan tactic was recognised as one by which a body of heavy infantry could countermarch to occupy same ground to their immediate rear and was subsequently adapted for that purpose, and that description is the (only) one which has come down to us. This would require that the adaptation of the Cretan countermarch into the *Tactica* manuals where it is found, omitted the missile-fire nature of the original tactic. Of course, in adapting and adopting such a countermarch for heavy phalangite infantry, such tactics would be unnecessary although it could be implied in the name. It would also be unnecessary to bring the less well armed and protected phalangites stationed at the rear of a formation to the front, except in rare circumstances. It may have been necessary, however, to have the phalanx turn to meet a threat in the rear, and thus a part of the Cretan countermarch would be ideal, and was recognised as such. It is also possible that commanders saw these tactics as used by the Cretan archer units, recognised their applicability and then adapted and adopted them for their phalanxes of heavy infantry, the origins of the manoeuvre remaining in its name. The archers too would need to countermarch to the left (as their later musketeer successors did), so to the left and not 'spearward' but this direction is logical and predicated by the next rank's bow.

Although it is possible that Cretan troops did use phalanxes or other types of troops, by the time of the domination of the Macedonian phalanx and the *Tactica* which described them, Cretan troops were overwhelmingly associated with the bow, so much so as we have seen that if Cretans are mentioned in our sources, they are usually assumed to be archers and if 'archers' alone are mentioned they often prove to be Cretans later in the same source or are assumed to be.

A Cretan countermarch for Cretan archers

Reading the Cretan countermarch in the way proposed here provides a tantalising suggestion for Cretan archery tactics and perhaps why units of Cretan archers became so common in armies from the late fifth century BCE onwards; they had a manoeuvre which required specific drill and training and which allowed them to keep up a constant volley of archery fire unmatched by other groups of archers. This reading also provides a link to the ubiquity of Cretan archers in armies of the period of the phalanx (and beyond), in that they had a countermarch named after them which was afterwards recognised as useful in more ways than one and adapted then adopted for use by heavy phalangites. This in itself suggests that phalanx tactics were not static but involved deep thought by various commanders and the application of practice and inspiration, just as William

Louis of Nassau would apply to Dutch musketeers in 1594 based on his reading of a tactical manual which had its origins almost 2,000 years earlier.

Further Reading

Geoffrey Parker *The Military Revolution*, Second Edition, (Cambridge, 1996).

Olaf van Nimwegen *The Dutch Army and the Military Revolutions 1588-1688*, translated by Andrew May (Woodbridge, Suffolk, 2010).

Olaf van Nimwegen "The Tactical Military Revolution and Dutch Army Operations during the Era of the Twelve Years Truce (1592-1618) in Randall Lesaffer (ed.) *The Twelve Years Truce (1609)* (Leiden, 2014), pp. 121-151.